

ACCOUNTING AND AUDIT OF FIXED ASSETS

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Annotation: The article deals with accounting and audit of fixed assets. The fixed assets formed at the initial stage of the activity of a trade organization require constant management. This management is carried out within the framework of accounting.

Keywords: accounting, accounting audit, fixed assets, financial condition, production assets

In modern economic conditions, one of the factors for the sustainable development of a trade organization is the improvement of the use of its property. The fixed assets involved in organizations serve as the most important economic resource for them and, of course, affect the performance of commercial activities.

The fixed assets formed at the initial stage of the activity of a trade organization require constant management. This management is carried out within the framework of accounting.

The relevance of the topic “Accounting and audit of fixed assets” is determined by the fact that, under the current taxation procedure, incorrect accounting of fixed assets leads to an increase in the cost of maintaining and maintaining the existing material and technical base, an increase in the tax burden, and a decrease in competitiveness compared to other market entities.

In addition, errors in accounting affect the financial condition of organizations. Most of the production assets, as a rule, are not used efficiently enough.

Irrational use of fixed assets leads to significant property tax payments. The situation is aggravated due to insufficiently active re-profiling of production capacities and misuse of depreciation charges included in expenses.

Property, plant and equipment is a piece of property used as a means of labor in the production of products, performance of work or provision of services, or for the management of an organization, for a period exceeding 12 months or a normal operating cycle.

The purpose of this work is to consider the issues of accounting and audit of fixed assets” and proposals for measures to improve the accounting of fixed assets.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- formulate the main differences in the interpretation of the concept of fixed assets in accounting and tax accounting;
- study the methodology for conducting an audit of fixed assets
- make an analysis of the main performance indicators of the enterprise and identify the role of accounting and control in improving the efficiency of the use of the enterprise's production resources;
- make recommendations on improving the system of accounting and audit of fixed assets”.

In the course of the audit, we found the following facts indicating a significant discrepancy between the internal control system and the scale and nature of its activities: there is no schedule of document flow for the accounting of fixed assets.

In order to achieve the goals of the audit of the availability and safety of fixed assets, based on the results of testing the internal control system, it was decided to conduct a detailed audit of fixed assets acquired in the course of the organization's activities. The sample was made by types of fixed assets in accordance - 5 objects of each type (by random sampling).

По поступившим и выбывшим в отчетном периоде объектам основных средств проводилась детальная проверка.

A detailed check of the calculation of depreciation of fixed assets, verification of calculations of the amounts of depreciation deductions, verification of the correspondence between the calculations of the amounts of depreciation deductions and the timing of depreciation, verification of the correctness of attributing fixed assets to depreciation groups, verification of operations for accounting for the repair of fixed assets was carried out. During the verification, no significant violations were found.

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